

Production of high purity hydrogen by sorption enhanced steam reforming of crude glycerol

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Abstract

Here we report effective production of pure hydrogen from crude glycerol by the one-stage sorption enhanced steam reforming (SESR) process. This process yielded H₂ up to 88% with a very high purity (99.7 vol%) at atmospheric pressure and at 550-600 °C with a steam/C = 3 in a fixed-bed reactor over a mixture of Ni/Co catalyst derived from hydrotalcite-like material (HT) and dolomite as CO₂ sorbent. The concentration of methane is lowest at 575 °C, while the CO concentration increases concurrently with increasing temperature from 525 to 600 °C. The high coking potential of glycerol and fatty acid methyl esters (C₁₇-C₁₉) resulted in the increased formation of coke, thus lower hydrogen yield. The reaction rates of methane reforming and water-gas shift reactions are much higher than the steam reforming of crude glycerol on Co-Ni catalysts. The high purity of hydrogen can be obtained even at low spatial times with low crude glycerol conversions. Our work reveals a great potential to directly convert biomass derived complex mixtures to the most clean energy carrier of hydrogen with high yield and purity.

Keywords: Crude glycerol, Hydrogen, Carbonation, Ni-Co catalyst, Sorption enhanced reforming

1. Introduction

Hydrogen has been considered as a potential clean and environmental friendly energy carrier for a sustainable growth of an increasingly energy dependent society. However, currently, hydrogen is mostly produced from fossil fuels (96%), which clearly are not sustainable and CO₂ neutral routes. Among them, steam reforming (SR) of natural gas represents the most employed process (48%). It is crucial to develop new technologies to produce hydrogen from

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renewable sources, such as biomass, at high energy efficiency, in an environmental friendly and cost attractive manner. Crude glycerol (CGLY), a by-product of biodiesel production (10-12 wt% of the total product) [1] has been increasingly produced in recent years as a consequence of the rapid growth in biodiesel production. Increasing availability and renewability of glycerol make it attractive to utilize glycerol as feedstock, e.g., for H₂ production [2-5]. To convert crude glycerol to hydrogen, different routes such as pyrolysis [6], gasification [7-9], aqueous phase reforming [10, 11] and catalytic steam reforming [12-17] have been investigated in recent years.

The integration of the water-gas shift (WGS) reaction and the CO₂ removal to the steam reforming (SR) reaction in a single reactor by incorporating a CaO-based sorbent in the catalyst bed has been shown as a promising approach to enhance the efficiency in the hydrogen production from biomass-derived products, such as pure [18] and crude glycerol [19]. We have previously reported that the hydrogen production with both purity and yield of approximately 99% was achieved by sorption enhanced steam reforming (SESR) of pure glycerol, at atmospheric pressure, 575 °C and steam/C ratio of 3 [18]. Dou et al. have recently illustrated that integration of SR of crude glycerol with *in-situ* CO₂ removal can produce hydrogen at about 90 vol% purity, with methane and CO in balance [19]. However, purification processes such as steam reforming of hydrocarbons, WGS reaction and CO₂ separation are still required for production of pure hydrogen, which limits its advantages and applications. Direct production of pure hydrogen is highly desired to simplify the processes, thus reduces the cost of hydrogen production. However, it is still a great challenge to produce almost pure hydrogen directly from crude glycerol due to its composition complexity. In addition, the H₂ yield from the SESR of crude glycerol has not been addressed so far. Dou et al. have presented another challenge in the conversion of crude glycerol, namely the very high coking potential due to presence of heavy compounds such as C₁₇-C₁₉ acid methyl esters [19]. The carbon or coke formation leads to catalyst deactivation and low hydrogen yield, since the hydrogen yield is very sensitive to coke formation.

From the ultimate analysis of crude glycerol (see Experimental part) the stoichiometry of the SESR reaction, after combining SR, WGS and carbonation reactions, would perform according to the following exothermic reaction:

Thus, the stoichiometric hydrogen yield, which represents the theoretical maximum by the combined SR and WGS reactions of the CGLY, would be 7.08 moles of hydrogen per mol of CGLY (or 143.5 g H₂ kg⁻¹_{CGLY}). We treated the crude glycerol mixture as a lumped compound, and the stoichiometric hydrogen yield was obtained by the C, H and O mass balances based on the C, H and O stoichiometric number of the mixture, thus regardless of the detailed composition of the crude glycerol mixture. The alternative reaction pathway to hydrogen from CGLY is the catalytic/thermal decomposition, which leads to only 4.47 moles of hydrogen per mol of CGLY. In addition, the pyrolysis of the crude glycerol mixture could form hydrocarbons (C_nH_m), mainly CH₄, in the product gas, and solid coke [20], which lower the hydrogen yield and should be suppressed.

Catalysts with high activity and selectivity are then crucial for obtaining high yield of hydrogen from SESR processes [4]. For the selective hydrogen production from C₂-C₆ oxygenated compounds, the formation of H₂ and CO through the C-C and C-H bonds cleavage, followed by the WGS reaction is the preferred pathway [21]. Hydrotalcite derived Co-Ni catalysts have been developed in our laboratory, which has been shown high C-C bond cleavage activity in SESR of different oxygenated compounds such as ethanol [22, 23], and pure glycerol [18] as well as biosyngas [24].

In this work we extend the single-stage SESR reaction to a much more complex and more realistic feedstock of crude glycerol, obtained directly from an industrial biodiesel plant as a by-product, in a fixed-bed reactor containing a mixture of Ni-Co catalyst derived from hydrotalcite-like material (HT) and calcined dolomite as CO₂ sorbent. The effects of operating parameters such as, temperature and spatial time, as well as the catalyst-sorbent cyclic stability, were experimentally evaluated, aiming at optimizing conditions towards higher hydrogen purity and yield. The SESR reaction integrated steam reforming of oxygenates and hydrocarbons, water gas shift reactions and carbonation reactions into one stage. The limiting reaction step to the high hydrogen yield is identified by a reaction pathway analysis based on the changes in hydrogen yield and selectivity with spatial time of CGLY in the reactor.

2. Experimental

2.1 Crude Glycerol (CGLY)

The crude glycerol (CGLY) used in the present work mainly consists of 70-90 wt% glycerol, with water and methanol contents lower than 15 wt%, inorganic salts lower than 5 wt% and polyglycerol impurities up to 5 wt%, based on the data sheet from Directive 2001/58/EC

provided by the manufacturer [19]. The water and methanol in the crude glycerol favors the production of hydrogen, so its removal step, which is often used for upgrading crude glycerol value, is avoided by using the reforming or our sorption enhanced reforming process. The content of C, H, N, S and O in the CGLY consisted of 36.2, 9.1, 0.1, 0.0 and 54.6 wt%, respectively [19]. From this analysis, the calculated average elemental molar formula, based on C, H and O, was therefore $C_{3\pm 0.2}H_{8.9\pm 0.4}O_{3.4\pm 0.2}$. The liquid density of the CGLY was measured as $1386 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ at $20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ compared to $1261 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ for pure glycerol [19]. In addition, the lower heating value (LHV) of the CGLY was $17.64 \text{ MJ}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$, slightly higher than that of the pure glycerol, $16.01 \text{ MJ}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$ [19]. The composition of the crude glycerol usually varies and depends on the crop or animal oils used as feedstock in the biodiesel synthesis. The higher density and heating value of the CGLY could be due to the presence of the following components in the sample: linoleic ($C_{19}H_{34}O_2$), palmitic ($C_{17}H_{34}O_2$), oleic ($C_{19}H_{36}O_2$), and stearic ($C_{19}H_{38}O_2$) acid methyl esters, revealed by a GC-MS spectrum of the CGLY [19]. The complexity of crude glycerol steam reforming is reflected by the many possible products that can be obtained: hydrogen, carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, methane, ethane, ethylene, acetaldehyde, acetic acid, acetone, methanol, acrolein, ethanol, allyl alcohol, formaldehyde, water and coke [7, 25].

The solid residue of biomass was measured by a temperature programmed oxidation in air ($50 \text{ Nml}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$) at a heating rate of $5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ up to $815 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in a thermogravimetric analyzer, (TGA, Netzsch-STA 449). A small amount of CGLY (20 mg) was placed in an alumina crucible and oxidized. A solid residue of 3.5 wt% was obtained, which is possibly the inorganic salts content of the crude glycerol (CGLY).

2.2 Catalyst preparation

The hydrotalcite-like material (HT) used as catalyst was prepared by co-precipitation of $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_3\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_3\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3\cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The stoichiometric ratio of cations was chosen to yield 40% total metal loading of Co and Ni, giving a material with the nominal composition 20%Ni–20%Co HT. The obtained precipitate was then filtered, dried and calcined to yield Co–Ni catalyst. After the calcination, the hydrotalcite structure was transferred into a mixed oxide [22]. A detailed description on preparation and characterization of the multifunctional catalyst used in the present work has previously been reported elsewhere [22]. The calcinated catalyst has a BET surface area of $94 \text{ m}^2\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ with an average pores size of 6 nm. The formation of Co-Ni alloy was confirmed by TPR and SEM-

EDX mapping [22] and the surface area of Co-Ni alloy is $23.3 \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$ measured by hydrogen chemisorption, corresponding to a dispersion of 8.7%.

2.3 CO_2 sorbent

Arctic dolomite, used as precursor of Ca for CO_2 capture was supplied by Franefoss Miljøkalk A/S, Norway. It is documented to have a purity of approximately 98.5 wt% $\text{CaMg}(\text{CO}_3)_2$ and no sulfur according to X-ray fluorescence analysis. The dolomite sample was calcined in a muffle oven in air flow at $900 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 4 h prior to its application as CO_2 sorbent. The initial maximum capacity for CO_2 capture was estimated at *ca.* 46% (mass of CO_2 captured /100 g of calcined sorbent).

2.4 Process tests

The experimental setup used in the SESR experiments of the crude glycerol is shown, as a schematic diagram, in Figure 1. It consists of a stainless steel fixed-bed reactor (i.d. 9 mm), which was loaded with a 12 g mixture of CO_2 sorbent (calcined dolomite) and Ni-Co/HT catalyst, at a sorbent/catalyst = 5 g/g. The reactant mixture was prepared with water to CGLY at a molar ratio of 9 (38 wt% CGLY, steam/C of 3). Lower water to CGLY ratios are limited by high viscosity, and also would cause carbon build up on the catalyst surface [26, 27]. The mixture were kept in a liquid storage and feed tank. Gas and liquid flows were controlled by Bronkhorst® mass flow controllers. There is a high potential of coke formation due to the presence of nonvolatile high molecular biodiesel (C_{17} - C_{19} oxygenates) as well as highly oxygenated glycerol in the vaporizer, which easily blocks the tubes and vaporizer. The cold mixture of crude glycerol and water is then directly injected to the top of reactor and directly vaporized at the top of the catalyst and sorbent bed.

A typical operation procedure is described as the following. Prior to the reforming reactions, the Ni-Co/HT catalyst was activated by reducing metal oxides under a flowing gas mixture of 50 vol% H_2 - N_2 with a total flow rate of $200 \text{ Nml} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$ at $670 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 10 h. After catalyst reduction, the reactor was purged with N_2 and cooled down to the desired reaction temperature (525 - $600 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). The reaction temperature was measured by a thermocouple inserted in the catalyst/sorbent bed. All the experiments were carried out at atmospheric pressure. The liquid reactant mixture, at a flow of 5 - $10 \text{ g} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$, was swept by 75 - $150 \text{ Nml} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$ N_2 flow to keep the N_2/C ratio constant, which also was employed as internal standard, directly to the liquid injector on the top of the reactor. The SESR of CGLY occurred until the calcined dolomite, as CO_2 sorbent, was saturated and lost its capacity for CO_2 removal.

Afterwards, the conventional SR and WGS reactions took place, which were allowed to reach the steady state to compare with SESR. The catalyst and sorbent were regenerated at 770 °C in air flow (200 Nml·min⁻¹), until CO₂ levels dropped less than 1 vol%. A lower temperature for the regeneration is always highly desired to achieve higher energy efficiency. The temperature of 770 °C was selected by preliminary experiments by taking into account the kinetic of the decarbonation of dolomites [23]. The effluent gas from the reactor was cooled down through a cooling tank, followed by a moisture separation through a membrane drier. The exiting gas was analyzed with an on-line Agilent® 3000 dual channel Micro GC, equipped with a Molsieve and Plot U columns and a TCD detector. The calculation of the product distribution was based on the dry composition in the gas effluent. The species detected were H₂, CH₄, CO and CO₂. The flow rates of these species were estimated based on the N₂ flow rate as the inert standard.

In this work, H₂ yield, H₂ purity and the catalyst selectivity to hydrogen were defined according to Eq. 2 to 4, respectively.

$$H_2 \text{ yield} = 100 \cdot \left[\frac{F_{H_2}}{7.08 \cdot F_{CGLY}} \right] \quad (2)$$

$$H_2 \text{ purity} = 100 \cdot \left[\frac{y_{H_2}}{\sum_i y_i} \right] \quad (3)$$

$$H_2 \text{ selectivity} = 100 \cdot \left[\frac{y_{H_2} \cdot 2}{y_{H_2} \cdot 2 + y_{CH_4} \cdot 4} \right] \quad (4)$$

Where F_{H_2} is the molar flow rate of H₂ (mol·min⁻¹), F_{CGLY} is the molar flow rate of CGLY (mol·min⁻¹), and y_i is the molar content (N₂ free and dry basis) of each specie i (H₂, CH₄, CO and CO₂). The F_{CGLY} was obtained by the 0.965 weight of crude glycerol divided by the molecular weight of C₃H_{8.95}O_{3.4}, where the inorganic salts (approximately 3.5 wt%) were subtracted by a factor of 0.965. The spatial time (τ) is defined as the ratio of the weight of catalyst bed to CGLY fed per hour (g_{catalyst}·g_{CGLY}⁻¹·h).

3. Results and discussion

3.1 High purity hydrogen from SESR of CGLY

Figure 2 shows a typical profile of the evolution of the product gas composition in a N₂ free and dry basis during a SESR experiment of CGLY over a mixture of the Ni-Co/HT catalyst and calcined dolomite as CO₂ sorbent. In this case, the experiment was carried out at 550 °C and 1 atm, with a steam/C = 3, at a liquid flow rate of 5 g·h⁻¹ ($\tau = 1.09$ h). Because of its nature, the SESR reaction has a very strong dependence on the CO₂ removal. It is well-known that the CaO-CO₂ reaction has a fast reaction regime, followed by a fairly slow reaction regime controlled by CO₂ diffusion through the layer of solid CaCO₃ product formed on the CaO [28, 29]. Figure 2, shows three regimes of the reaction with time on stream, namely pre-breakthrough, breakthrough and post-breakthrough. In the pre-breakthrough regime, the most of CO₂ generated by steam reforming and water-gas shift reactions was removed by the fast carbonation reaction with CaO, and led to a significant sorption enhancement to hydrogen production. The breakthrough period reflects the transition of the CaO carbonation from the first fast reaction to the second diffusion controlled and relatively slow regime. When the CaO became saturated, the sorption enhancement disappeared in the post-breakthrough regime, and products are dominated by SR as well as the WGS reaction.

In the pre-breakthrough period, very low CO and CO₂ concentrations were observed as a result of shifted WGS equilibrium toward H₂ production by *in-situ* CO₂ removal. The methane concentration was also much lower during the pre-breakthrough period than during the post-breakthrough, where the conventional SR reaction takes place. It can be a result of enhanced reforming of CH₄, or/and suppressed CO methanation by lowering CO concentration caused by *in-situ* CO₂ removal, which could not be distinguished in the present work. No oxygenates were detected in both the gas phase and the condensed water, suggesting 100% conversion of the mixed oxygenates. In contrast to work of Valliyappan et al. [7], no large hydrocarbons (C₁⁺) were detected at both the SESR and SR conditions in the present work. These results reflect a high C-C bond cleavage ability of the Ni-Co catalyst, and thus the high activity of large oxygenates and heavy hydrocarbon reforming reactions. As a consequence, a high H₂ purity (99.7 vol%) was achieved with a very low concentration of methane.

3.2 Effects of temperature on hydrogen purity and yield

Table 1 summarizes the experimental results obtained during the SESR process of CGLY at atmospheric pressure and temperatures between 525-600 °C. Very high selectivity of the catalyst to H₂ production (>99%) was obtained, with a relatively weak dependence on the temperature. CO concentration decreased concurrently with decreasing temperature, which

might be a consequence of favorable thermodynamics of WGS reaction at lower temperatures. The minimum CO₂ concentration was achieved at 550 °C as a result of a balance between the fast carbonation kinetics at relatively high temperatures and favorable thermodynamics at low temperatures. The exothermic carbonation reaction is unfavorable at high temperatures, where the carbonation kinetics could be also lowered by lower driving forces between the CO₂ pressures in the gas phase and CO₂ equilibrium pressure. This led to a weaker sorption enhancement at 600 °C, reflecting a higher concentration of CO₂ and CH₄ and lower H₂ purity. On the other hand, it further confirms the synergistic effect between the catalytic SR and CO₂ carbonation reactions in the sorbent/catalyst bed, being the clear advantages of the sorption enhanced reaction leading to an enhanced H₂ production by shifting the equilibrium of water-gas shift reaction. The highest H₂ purity (99.7 vol%) was achieved at both 550 and 575 °C, but 550 °C is a preferable operating temperature in terms of the lower CO concentration (1.2×10^{-2} vol% in Table 1), although the methane concentration is lower at 575 °C.

The higher H₂ purity (99.7 vol% at 575 °C and steam/C = 3) was obtained comparing to the results obtained for SESR of pure glycerol [18] at the same experimental conditions (approximately 99 vol%). It could be ascribed to the presence of oxygenates with high carbon numbers, such as C₁₇-C₁₉ esters [21]. Thermodynamic analysis has indicated that the sorption enhancement on H₂ production is more pronounced for the large oxygenates [21]. In addition, the presence of methanol in crude glycerol could also contribute to the obtained high H₂ purity, due to its higher reactivity comparing to the C₂₊ oxygenated hydrocarbons. Methanol reforming does not require C-C bond cleavage and has low tendency to methane formation [30].

The spatial time (τ) used in the present work (1.09 h) for the study of the temperature effect is similar to the one used in the aqueous reforming of sorbitol, glycerol and ethylene glycol on Ni [31] and Pt based catalysts [32]. SESR of CGLY is superior to the aqueous reforming in terms of H₂ purity and yield [31, 32]. However, a comparison of the energy efficiency between the two processes is not straightforward, which needs to be further investigated.

3.3 Effects of spatial time

The effect of the spatial time was studied by adjusting the flow rates of the liquid reactant mixture (CGLY and water) and N₂ on the same amount of catalysts and sorbents for all the experiments. Figure 3 shows the effect of the spatial time (τ) on the H₂ yield (%) and purity

(vol.%) during the SESR of CGLY at 550 °C and atmospheric pressure. The H₂ purity remained nearly constant (99.5-99.7 vol.%), whilst the H₂ yield decreased drastically from 88.1 to 45.3%, when τ was decreased from 1.09 to 0.54 h. The methane and CO contents are only slightly increased with increasing the spatial time. The SESR reaction integrated steam reforming of oxygenates and hydrocarbons, water gas shift reaction and carbonation reaction into one stage. The results (Figure 3) indicate the reaction rate of water-gas shift and methane reforming are high enough making reactions close to equilibrium at the conditions studied [18]. However, the yield of H₂ decreased almost linearly with decreasing **spatial** time, suggesting a much lower reaction rate of CGLY reforming than ones of methane reforming and water-gas shift reactions. It reveals that the CGLY reforming with the C-C bond cleavage is the limiting step for the hydrogen production. The activity of the reforming catalysts for the oxygenate reforming, in particular the C-C bond cleavage activity, should be further improved.

3.4 Coke formation and materials stability

The hydrogen yield in this work is limited to between 85-88% at τ of 1.09 h, which is lower comparing to the c.a. 99% of hydrogen yield obtained from SESR of pure glycerol at the same steam/C ratio of 3 [18]. It is most likely a result of carbonaceous materials formation from CGLY, such as coke. The poor stability of heavy components in CGLY (for instance, fatty acid methyl esters) as impurities in crude glycerol could lead to the pyrolysis reactions in the gas phase front the catalytic bed, promoting the coke formation. This behavior is in agreement with those observed by Dou and co-workers who reported by TGA pyrolysis experiments [33] and SESR experiments [19] that crude glycerol yielded larger carbonaceous residues than pure glycerol.

Figure 4 shows a typical distribution of carbon formed along the catalysts bed, indicated by the changes in the color of the sample collected from the top to the bottom of the reactor bed (from left to right in the figure). The most of the carbonaceous materials were formed on the top of the catalyst/acceptor bed as well as the wall at the reactor inlet. The poorly stable heavier reactants could form oxygenated intermediates by pyrolysis at the inlet of the reactor, which could convert to either gases or coke. When the **spatial** time was decreased, coke formed also in a relatively deep bed in the reactor. In the sample close to the bottom of the reactor, the black particles are the Ni-Co catalyst. The more detailed characterization of coke will be discussed below. However, it should be noted that the hydrogen yield and purity,

instead of composition only, should be studied in the steam reforming or sorption enhanced reforming, which is often ignored in the literature.

Carbonaceous deposits at the top of the material bed were collected after the SESR of CGLY at 550 °C and **spatial** times of 1.09 and 0.73 h, and passed to SEM-EDX and RAMAN spectroscopic study to gain the insight of the nature of the carbonaceous material formed in the reaction. Figure 5a shows a Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) image and the Energy Dispersive X-ray (EDX) microanalysis of the formed coke on top of the catalyst-**sorbent** bed. Coke was mainly composed by C (>59 wt.%), which was deposited at the top of the bed, and also on the surface of the catalyst particles, represented by the presence of Al, Ni and Co (\approx 2-3 wt.%) in the collected coke. It should be pointed that a high Na presence (17 wt.%) in the coke, which obviously comes from the inorganic salts (NaOH) in the crude glycerol. The NaOH is often used as the catalyst in biodiesel production. Figure 5b exhibits the UV Raman spectra of the coke formed after the SESR of CGLY at τ of 1.09 h (b-1) and 0.73 h (b-2), respectively, in which the two first-order more representative bands of carbonaceous materials appear. **The first**, at around 1400 cm^{-1} is caused by defects and disorder in the graphene-like structure and is denoted as D band. The G band at 1600 cm^{-1} is associated with graphite sheets. The intensity ratio of the bands, I_D/I_G , gives a measure of the degree of crystallinity of the graphite layers. The low I_D/I_G ratio (\approx 0.52) for carbonaceous deposits formed at high **spatial** time (1.09 h) observed in the first spectrum, (b-1), would correspond to a high-graphitic coke with only few structural defects. Microelemental analysis was also carried out in order to find out the hydrogen content in the coke. The amount of C, H and O consisted of 39.9, 0.5 and 59.6 wt%, respectively, which gives a C/H molar ratio of 7.13, which is in **line** with the highly graphitic structure revealed by RAMAN. However, in the case of the carbonaceous deposits formed at lower **spatial** time the I_D/I_G ratio increases up to 0.77 (Figure 5 b-2), revealing a more disordered structure. In this case, C, H and O contents in the coke were 53.8, 4.4 and 41.8 wt%, respectively, with a C/H molar ratio of 1.03, pointing out a less graphitized coke with higher H content.

Based on the above results and discussions, we summarize the main challenges in the SESR of crude glycerol, namely carbon formation due to the presence of non-volatile heavy compounds, such as C_{17} - C_{19} acid methyl esters, and accumulation of alkaline due to the presence of Na(OH). Therefore, the cycle stability of the catalyst and the CO_2 **sorbents** could be a challenge in the SESR of CGLY due to the complexity of the feedstock. Three cycles of SESR of CGLY were performed, 550 °C SESR reaction and 770 °C regeneration in air, to test

the stability of the catalyst and CO₂ sorbent. There are two reasons to use air in the regeneration. The first is air being much cheaper comparing to other inert gases or steam, which dilutes the CO₂ released thus lower the decarbonation temperature of the dolomites. The second is that oxygen in the air could burn off the coke deposits at the top of the bed and on the catalyst surface, which regenerates the catalysts, and partially provides heat for the decarbonation of the dolomites. Figure 6 shows the evolution of the H₂ and CO₂ concentrations in a N₂ free and dry basis, where CO and CH₄ concentrations were not plotted, because they followed a similar trend to CO₂. During the pre-breakthrough, the H₂ (99.7 vol%) and CO₂ (1.0-1.6 x10⁻² vol%) concentrations kept on the same levels after 3 cycles, indicating no significant deactivation of the catalyst, although a relatively high content of Na was detected in the carbonaceous deposits. A slight decrease in the breakthrough time of CO₂ (Figure 6) and rather similar slopes of the breakthrough curves in these three cycles are observed, suggesting a mild change in the kinetics and CO₂ capture capacity, which is similar to that observed in SESR of methane [34, 35], and ethanol [23]. The CO₂ breakthrough time decreases slightly with increasing cycle number as a result of a loss of the CO₂ capacity of the sorbents [23, 34, 35]. The amount of CO₂ captured was calculated as the difference of the flow rate of CO₂ (g·min⁻¹) between the SR and SESR regimes, multiplied by the breakthrough time (min). The capture capacities, defined as the mass of CO₂ captured per 100 g of calcined dolomite, observed in this work were 43.3, 37.4 and 34.5 % for cycles 1, 2 and 3, respectively. Although the deactivation of carbonation was observed, the deactivation rate was found to be much slower comparing to one in the SESR of ethanol, where almost 50% lost of the CaO activity was found after the first cycle [23]. This might suggest that not only no significant deactivation of the Ni-Co catalysts after 3 reaction-regeneration cycles was caused by the inorganic salts in the crude glycerol but also that the presence of these salts could have some positive effect on the stability of the dolomite in the carbonation-decarbonation cycles. However, the effects of inorganic salts on the long term stability of both catalysts and CO₂ sorbents need to be investigated in a more detail in future studies.

4. Conclusions

High purity (99.7 vol%) and high yield (88%) H₂ can be produced directly from crude glycerol in a single-step SESR process on Ni-Co catalysts, where *in-situ* removal of CO₂ by dolomite greatly enhanced reforming reactions and water-gas shift reactions. The reaction rates of methane reforming and water-gas shift reactions are much higher than the steam reforming of crude glycerol on Ni-Co catalysts. Take advantages of high activity of water-gas

shift reaction at the conditions with *in-situ* CO₂ removal, the high purity of hydrogen can be obtained at relatively low **spatial** time, or at low crude glycerol conversions. The results also reveal that future research needs to improve the catalyst activity for steam reforming of crude glycerol.

In addition, although the CO level (about 100 ppm) in the H₂ stream obtained from the SESR of the crude glycerol is still slightly high for its application in low temperature fuel cells, many other fuel cell technologies, such as high temperature fuel cells and acid fuel cells, can benefit from such high purity of hydrogen [36]. However, it will be of great interests to optimize the materials, operating conditions and reactor design to further reduce the coke formation and the CO concentration for the application in low temperature fuel cells.

More importantly, the SESR of crude glycerol with a complex composition can be considered as a model system, which has demonstrated that could have great potential to upgrade other biomass derived complex mixtures such as bio-oils to high purity hydrogen. It is believed that SESR will play an important role in future biomass conversion to clean energy.

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Table 1. Effect of the reaction temperature on the characteristics of the product gas during SESR of CGLY; P = 1 atm; τ = 1.09 h; steam/C = 3, Sorbent/Catalyst = 5 g/g

	Temperature (°C)			
	525	550	575	600
H ₂ selectivity (%) ^a	99.1	99.4	99.9	99.8
H ₂ yield (%) ^b	85.1	88.1	87.7	87.9
Gas composition (vol%) ^c				
H ₂	99.5	99.7	99.7	99.2
CH ₄	0.4	2.9 x10 ⁻¹	4.4 x10 ⁻²	0.1
CO	1.0 x10 ⁻²	1.2 x10 ⁻²	5.1 x10 ⁻²	1.9 x10 ⁻¹
CO ₂	9.0 x10 ⁻²	1.6 x10 ⁻²	2.1 x10 ⁻¹	5.2 x10 ⁻¹

^a H₂ Selectivity (% mol): [number of H atoms in H₂ produced / number of H atoms in the product gas] x 100

^b H₂ yield (% mol): [number of moles of H₂ in the product gas / 7.08 x moles of CGLY fed] x 100

^c Gas composition (% vol): dry and N₂ free basis

Figure Legend

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the SESR experimental setup.

Figure 2. Evolution of the gas product composition (N₂ free and dry basis) from the SESR to SR reaction of CGLY. Experimental conditions: 550 °C, 1 atm; steam/C = 3, τ = 1.09 h; 2 g of 20%Ni-20%Co/HT catalyst (sorbent/catalyst = 5 g/g).

Figure 3. Effect of the spatial time, τ , (h) on the H₂ yield and purity during the SESR of CGLY. Experimental conditions: 550 °C and 1 atm; steam/C = 3; 2 g of 20%Ni-20%Co/HT catalyst (sorbent/catalyst = 5 g/g).

Figure 4. Catalyst/sorbent sample collected from the top to the bottom of the reactor bed after a SESR experiment of CGLY. Experimental conditions: 550 °C, 1 atm; steam/C = 3, τ = 1.09 h; 2 g of 20%Ni-20%Co/HT catalyst (sorbent/catalyst = 5 g/g).

Figure 5. SEM image and EDX microanalysis (a) and UV Raman spectra (b) of the coke collected from the top of the catalyst/sorbent bed after SESR of CGLY. Experimental conditions: 550 °C, 1 atm; steam/C = 3; 2 g of 20%Ni-20%Co/HT catalyst (sorbent/catalyst = 5 g/g); τ = 1.09 h (a) and (b-1), and 0.73 h (b-2).

Figure 6. Evolution of the H₂ and CO₂ contents in the 3 repeated cycles from the SESR to SR reaction using CGLY. Experimental conditions: 550 °C and 1 atm; steam/C = 3, τ = 1.09 h; 2 g of 20%Ni-20%Co/HT catalyst (sorbent/catalyst = 5 g/g). \diamond, \blacklozenge : first cycle; \square, \blacksquare : second cycle; Δ, \blacktriangle : third cycle, respectively.

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

Figure 5.

Figure 6.